

MEDICAL SCIENCES

A METHOD FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH PARTIAL ADENTIA AND PERIODONTAL DISEASES BEFORE PROSTHETICS

Aliyev M.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Jalilova G.,

*Department of Pediatric Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Davudova M.

*Azerbaijan Medical University,
Department of Orthopedic Dentistry. hourly paid teacher
Baku, Azerbaijan*

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Abstract

Considering the problem of quality of life directly in patients with adentia, we can say that today there is quite convincing evidence that tooth loss is associated with a deterioration in the quality of life associated with oral health. These results are independent of the context and measurement tool used.

The influence of general sanitation and specialized measures to prepare the oral cavity for prosthetics in periodontal diseases on the dental status and quality of life of patients with partial absence of teeth was studied.

Keywords: periodontitis, partial absence of teeth, preprosthetic preparation

Introduction

Periodontal diseases in terms of prevalence and medical and social significance occupy the first place in the structure of dental pathology of oral diseases. [2, 3]. Studies of domestic and foreign scientists confirm that the chronic course of periodontal disease leads to the loss of a large number of teeth, which entails significant violations of the masticatory apparatus. A chronic inflammatory process in most cases leads to intoxication and changes in the reactivity of the whole organism as a whole [4, 5].

The purpose of the study was to determine the degree of influence of pre-prosthetic preparation of the oral cavity in periodontal diseases on the dental status and quality of life of patients with partial absence of teeth.

Research methodology

To solve the set tasks, we conducted an examination and orthopedic treatment of 100 people recruited from the dispensary observation groups for periodontal diseases, and 35 people who applied to the dental clinic for prosthetics. The purpose of examining an orthopedic patient was to identify the etiology and development of the disease, to establish the degree and nature of morphological and functional disorders of the dental system, the relationship and interaction of these disorders with other organs and systems. The traditional scheme for examining patients with dental pathology includes a survey, examination, palpation, auscultation and occlusal diagnosis. The survey was conducted according to a certain scheme and in a certain sequence. The main complaints that patients made were: the absence of several teeth; difficulty chewing food; tooth

mobility; bleeding; aesthetic dissatisfaction due to destroyed teeth, changes in color, shape and size or existing orthopedic structures; breakdown of orthopedic appliances. Some patients complained after prosthetics of a burning sensation, tightness, pain under the prosthesis, the appearance of edema, redness, and impaired diction. When collecting an anamnesis of the disease, attention was paid to the period of removal of the last tooth, for which it was removed; probable causes, manifestation of the disease earlier, the nature and characteristics of the course. Particular attention in the collection of anamnesis was paid to establishing the statute of limitations for periodontal treatment, whether it was carried out at all or not. Also, during the conversation, the question of previous orthopedic treatment was clarified: did the patient previously use removable dentures, and to what extent it suited him [7]. Periodontal condition was characterized by the absence or presence of periodontal pockets, their depth, the presence or absence of supra- and subgingival dental deposits, bleeding, hyperesthesia [10.11]. In case of partial absence of teeth, the characteristics of dentition defects were carried out using the following criteria: localization and extent of defects; assessment of the state of the alveolar ridge included in the defect (atrophy, the presence of exostoses). When conducting occlusal diagnostics, the ratio of teeth and dentitions was characterized by the type of occlusion, premature contacts, dentoalveolar elongation, deformation of the occlusal surface of teeth and prostheses, overlap depth in the frontal region, the presence or absence of abrasion facets, the usefulness of existing dentures, and also determined the height of

the lower third faces. Special dental assessment methods included the determination of: the intensity of caries according to the KPU index; communal periodontal index CPI; simplified index of oral hygiene IGR-U; mobility according to A. I. Evdokimov; chewing efficiency; orthopantomography. In addition to the generally accepted dental examination, we conducted a targeted study of the functional state of the dentoalveolar system. It was carried out according to the "Hamburg test" program, taking into account the frequency of detection of six test features [1.12]. Chewing efficiency was determined according to the modified functional test of I. S. Rubinov (chewing on one side of the test product - hazelnut 0.8 g - until the swallowing reflex) with an analysis of the duration of chewing and the number of chewing movements [8]. For the normal duration of chewing a nut, 14 s was considered. Orthopantomography was performed for all orthopedic patients with extensive and multiple dentition defects using Planmeca Proline XC and OP100D orthopantomographs (Finland). It allows you to identify the relationship between teeth, roots, alveolar processes [9]. The state of psychological comfort was determined using the OHIP-14 questionnaire. The processing of the information array was carried out on a personal computer using a professional statistical software package: "Bio-stat"; "MS EXCELL v 7.0" for "Windows" products "Microsoft", "Statistic v. 6.0" for "Windows" by "Stat Soft, Inc" [6]. Patients with aggravated periodontal status complained of unpleasant sensations in the mouth, bleeding gums when brushing their teeth. During visual examination, supra- and subgingival dental deposits were recorded, bleeding of the gums was noted during probing. Oral hygiene in these patients was significantly worse compared to the group without periodontal diseases, IGR-U in group I was 3.1. The intensity of periodontal disease according to the CPI index (community periodontal index) in patients with periodontal disease was 2.6. When determining the chewing efficiency in patients with periodontal diseases, the number of chewing movements when chewing the test product (walnut 0.8 g) to the swallowing reflex was 25.3 ± 1.6 , the duration of chewing was 29.5 ± 1.8 s. healthy 20.9 ± 1.4 and 24.9 ± 1.8 s. respectively. Examination of patients under the "Hamburg test" program revealed a decrease in the functional state of the dentoalveolar system (ZChS) due to the partial absence of teeth, mainly in persons with periodontal diseases. The average indicator of the detection of the frequency of test signs in one examined was 1.4 ± 0.2 signs per one examined in group I versus 0.8 ± 0.2 in group II without periodontal disease. Among the pathological signs, the asynchrony of occlusal sound during the closing of the dentition, the trauma of eccentric occlusion, and palpation of the masticatory muscles prevailed. There were no significant intergroup differences in the analysis of chewing efficiency and the "Hamburg test" between the groups. In patients with periodontal diseases, mostly severe, there was a significant mobility of the teeth: within the 2nd-3rd degree. As a rule, all patients were diagnosed with traumatic occlusion due to the displacement and loss of individual teeth, deformations of the dentition were noted. Elimination of occlusal disorders in case of

dentition defects was an integral part of the special preparation of the oral cavity for prosthetics. The elimination of occlusal disorders pursued the following goals: normalization of occlusal relationships and movements of the lower jaw; elimination of functional overload of periodontal teeth; normalization of the function of masticatory muscles and temporomandibular joints; creation of conditions for the manufacture of a rational design of the prosthesis. Normalization of the occlusal relationships of the dentition was achieved by: grinding the tubercles of the displaced teeth; shortening of teeth that violate occlusion, with preliminary removal of the pulp; increase in interalveolar height; the imposition of special caps and prostheses that cause the restructuring of the alveolar process; removal of teeth or teeth and alveolar process (surgical method). The decrease in the functional state of the dentoalveolar system was reflected in the indicators of assessing the quality of life according to the OHIP-14 questionnaire. The analysis of questionnaires showed that the quality of life of patients with partial absence of teeth was reduced in all orthopedic patients. In persons with periodontal diseases, it approached an unsatisfactory level, which was 32.9 points, and in persons without them, it approached a satisfactory level: 23.2. Significant influence in answering questions on the proposed test was provided by poor nutrition and difficulties during eating, difficulty in speaking, as well as discomfort during communication with people, including at work, due to the absence of teeth. On average, testing in the structure of negative impact on quality of life identified the most important questions that influenced the results of testing: Do you have difficulty pronouncing words due to problems with your teeth, oral mucosa, or prostheses? Do you experience discomfort due to problems with your teeth, oral mucosa or dentures? Do you have to completely drop out of life because of problems with your teeth, oral mucosa or dentures? Do you have difficulty eating because of problems with your teeth, oral mucosa, or dentures? Do you feel uncomfortable communicating with people because of problems with your teeth, oral mucosa, or dentures? During testing, when answering these questions, most patients gave a positive answer.

Research results and discussion

General sanitation and specialized measures to prepare the oral cavity for prosthetics have made a significant contribution to the improvement of patients with periodontal diseases. After the treatment, changes occurred in the structure of the KPU index due to an increase in the number of filled teeth, although the values of the index itself remained unchanged. So, in the group of patients without periodontal disease, it was 13.6, and in chronic generalized periodontitis - 15.2. An analysis of clinical observations showed that periodontal indices reflect local changes in the oral cavity, which makes it possible to assess the degree of the inflammatory process and the severity of its course. Based on the dynamics of clinical indices, it was found that the highest severity of the inflammatory process was observed in patients with periodontitis of moderate and severe severity. After carrying out general sanitation measures

during the control examination before prosthetics, patients with a burdened periodontal status did not complain, the oral mucosa acquired a pale pink color. When probing, there was practically no bleeding of the gums, with the exception of persons with a severe form of periodontal disease. It should be noted that oral hygiene also improved significantly, as evidenced by the decrease in the IGR-U index. In patients with periodontal disease, it was 0.5, and in conditionally healthy individuals - 0.2. According to the CPI index in patients with periodontal diseases, there was also a positive trend due to a decrease in bleeding gums and a decrease in periodontal pockets, it amounted to 1.3. After the periodontal treatment, there was a slight increase in chewing efficiency: the number of chewing movements when chewing the test product to the swallowing reflex was 23.4 ± 1.4 with a chewing duration of 28.7 ± 1.2 c. Also, after carrying out preparatory measures for prosthetics, a second examination of patients according to the "Hamburg test" program improved the average rate of detection of the frequency of test signs in one examined, which was 1.1 ± 0.1 signs per one examined in group I versus 0.6 ± 0.2 in group II without periodontal disease. Also, when the analysis of chewing efficiency and the "Hamburg test" were repeated, there were no significant intergroup differences between the groups. In patients with periodontal diseases, tooth mobility decreased to 1–2 degrees after selective grinding according to the method proposed by D. Jankelson, 1955, and shortening of individual teeth or a group of teeth that violate occlusion, c by preliminary removal of the pulp. After the specialized and general sanitation measures in the oral cavity, the psychological comfort of patients both with and without periodontal diseases increased. Analysis of the questionnaires showed that the answers to some questions revealed a slightly positive trend. That is, the same issues that were identified in the primary study, and made up the structure of the negative impact on the quality of life of dental patients. Some of the questions that touched on pain and irritability associated with dental discomfort showed a positive trend in the psychological comfort of patients.

Findings

Thanks to testing, it was found that after pre-prosthetic preparation of the oral cavity, the state of psychological comfort of patients increased by an average of 21% in people with chronic periodontal diseases, and by 23% in people with conditionally healthy periodontium. To restore chewing efficiency in full, high-quality treatment is necessary by restoring the partial absence of teeth with orthopedic structures. But on the basis of the study, it can be concluded that general sanitation and specialized measures have a positive effect in preparing for prosthetics, the importance and necessity of

their implementation, which is confirmed by the improvement in hygienic and periodontal indices in people with chronic periodontal diseases: IGR-U - by 16%, and CPI by 12%. which, of course, affects the state of psychological comfort of patients.

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